

Synthesis of complexes of 2-(benzooxazolyl-2-aminoimino)-1,2-diphenylethanone with some bivalent transition metal ions

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A series of metal complexes having composition $[M(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}$ and $[M(\text{BOAIDE})\text{L}_3]\text{Cl}$, where HBOAIDE is a Schiff base ligand, derived from 2-hydrazinobenzooxazole and benzil, $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, and $L = \text{pyridine}$ or $\text{picoline}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ have been synthesized. The ligand acts as a monobasic tridentate donor, coordinating through azomethine nitrogen, ring oxygen atom and oxygen atom of benzil after deprotonation via tautomerization.

The electronic spectra indicate the complexes to be in an approximately octahedral environment, the symmetry being O_h for the Co^{II} and D_{4h} for others. Various crystal field parameters for the Co^{II} and distortion parameters for the Ni^{II} complexes on the basis of proposed geometry have been calculated.

Survey of literature reveals that though numerous work has been done with hydrazone ligands, the ligational behavior of hydrazone of benzooxazole moiety containing benzil has not been studied as yet¹. As a part of our continuing research on the coordination chemistry of NOS/NO donor group², we report here the ligational behavior of the ligand 2-(benzooxazolyl-2-aminoimino)-1,2-diphenylethanone (HBOAIDE) with $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} .

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are microcrystalline coloured powders having melting point higher than the ligand. They are stable at room temperature and have medium solubility in solvents like DMF, DMSO and THF. The molar conductance values ($63\text{--}74 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) are indicative of their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature.

The electronic spectra of the ligand reveal three bands at 250, 230 and 275 nm assigned respectively to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions with extensive conjugation³. ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand show a complex multiplet at δ 7.47–7.97 corresponding to 14 aromatic protons of the three phenyl groups and one proton of the secondary amino group⁴. ¹³C NMR spectra of the ligand show a complex multiplet at δ 127–194 corresponding to 17 carbons present in the compound under different magnetic environment⁵.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % :		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
		Found	Calcd.	
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}$	Brown	12.85	(12.67)	63.24
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}$	Brown	12.00	(12.14)	67.41
$[\text{Co}(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}$	Brown	12.04	(12.20)	61.05
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{Py})_3]\text{Cl}$	Pink	9.37	(9.41)	68.22
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{Py})_3]\text{Cl}$	Yellow	8.73	(8.56)	68.31
$[\text{Co}(\text{BOAIDE})(\text{Py})_3]\text{Cl}$	Green	8.76	(8.60)	62.87
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BOAIDE})(\alpha\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Yellow	8.79	(8.82)	71.57
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BOAIDE})(\beta\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Yellow	8.79	(8.82)	74.02
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BOAIDE})(\gamma\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Yellow	8.79	(8.82)	73.90
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BOAIDE})(\alpha\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Green	8.24	(8.18)	72.34
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BOAIDE})(\beta\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Green	8.24	(8.18)	73.01
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BOAIDE})(\gamma\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Green	8.24	(8.18)	71.86
$[\text{Co}(\text{BOAIDE})(\alpha\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Brown	8.21	(8.24)	64.34
$[\text{Co}(\text{BOAIDE})(\beta\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Brown	8.21	(8.24)	63.77
$[\text{Co}(\text{BOAIDE})(\gamma\text{-Pic})_3]\text{Cl}$	Brown	8.21	(8.24)	63.91

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and Cl analyses.

IR spectra of 2-hydrazinobenzooxazole exhibit a strong band at 3239cm^{-1} due to asymmetric stretching mode of NH_2 group being overlapped with secondary amino group and NH_2 group owing to their overlapping nature. A multiple band system of medium intensity is observed at 1616 (C–C), 1460 (C=N cyclic), 1278 (C–N cyclic) and 1212 (C–O–C) cm^{-1} , which may be due to ring stretching vibrational mode of benzooxazole moiety⁶. The N–H bending vibration for primary amine⁷ appears at $1600\text{--}1575 \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Other bands are observed at 1630 (N–H bending), 1235(C–N exocyclic) and 1003 cm^{-1} (N–N).

Reaction of 2-hydrazinobenzooxazole with benzil brings about significant changes in the spectra of the product. The most notable feature of the spectrum is the disappearance of bands at 3239 and 1630 cm^{-1} and appearance of additional bands at 3352 (NH), 3064 (C–H phenyl ring), 1660 (C=O) and 1594 cm^{-1} (C=N), suggesting thereby the condensation of 2-hydrazinobenzooxazole with benzil in 1 : 1 proportion with conversion of NH_2 group to azomethine group.

The Schiff base ligand shows band at 1616 (C=N cyclic), 1460 (C=C), 1278 (C–N cyclic) and 1212 cm^{-1} (C–O–C). The former three bands remain practically unaltered in the complexes indicating the noncoordination of ring nitrogen atom to metal ions, whereas the position of $\nu_{\text{C-O-C}}$ band shifts by 10–20 cm^{-1} in all the complexes, indicating coordination of ring oxygen atom to metal ions⁸.

In the spectra of the complexes the band due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ is absent and two new bands of medium intensity are observed at 1554 (C=C) and 1653 cm^{-1} (C–O), indicating that the ligand coordinates through deprotonation of enolic OH after enolization⁹. The bands at 1554 (C=N) and 1003 cm^{-1} (N–N) are found to be absent and a new band due to $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ (azo group) appears at 1585 cm^{-1} , indicating thereby coordination of one of the nitrogen atoms of the azo group with the metal ion¹⁰. This is further supported by the disappearance of the band at 3352 cm^{-1} (N–H). Thus IR spectra of the ligand as well as its metal complexes provide evidence of coordination of ligand through conversion of keto form to enolic form (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

A pair of bands of moderate intensity is observed at 450 (M–N) and 520 cm^{-1} (M–O) in all the complexes¹¹. Presence of a broad band at 3434 cm^{-1} confirms the presence of coordinated water in the complexes as evidenced by thermal analysis¹². The presence of pyridine (picoline) in coordination sphere is indicated by the disappearance of $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ band due to coordinated water and appearance of a band at 642 cm^{-1} assignable to in-plane ring deformation mode of coordinated pyridine (picoline)¹³.

All the complexes decomposed in an identical pattern. The first weight-loss was seen around $\sim 170^\circ$ corresponding

to three water molecules as evidenced by the occurrence of an endothermic peak, indicating them to be coordinated water. The anhydrous complexes remained stable up to 410° and then continued to decompose till 450° to give their stable oxides. The general pattern of thermal stability is found to be $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ complexes.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are 4.84, 3.21 and 1.82 B.M., respectively.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex showed a band system at ~ 9600 , ~ 19500 and $\sim 21000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to octahedral field transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, respectively¹⁴. The transition ratio ν_2/ν_1 , Dq , B and β for the complex were found to be 2.1–2.2, 11200 cm^{-1} , 780 cm^{-1} and 0.84, respectively. The β value lies lower than one, indicating greater covalency in metal-ligand bond.

The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complex is consistent with tetragonal geometry showing four bands at ~ 9000 , ~ 10500 , ~ 16000 and $\sim 24500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be due to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, respectively. The splitting of ν_1 band due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ transition suggests distortion from O_h symmetry to D_{4h} . The values of tetragonal parameters Dt , in and out plane field strength D_q^E and D_q^A were found to be 182.5, 10450 and 715 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The magnetic moment value of the Cu^{II} complex (1.82 B.M.) is in agreement with d^9 -configuration. Although the magnetic moment is poorly diamagnetic, the value excludes the possibility of tetrahedral structure which otherwise requires a value of >2.0 B.M. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex showed a broad asymmetric band at 14500 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$. Besides, the spectra possess a charge transfer band at higher frequency at 26500 cm^{-1} . So, Cu^{II} complex is most probably in six-coordinated environment with symmetry lower than octahedral.

ESR spectra of the Cu^{II} complex exhibited well resolved anisotropic signals in parallel and perpendicular ${}^{63}\text{Cu}$ region. The magnetic and bonding parameters deduced from the spectra are $g_{\parallel} = 2.31$, $g_{\perp} = 2.06$, $g_{\text{av}} = 2.162$, $A_{\parallel} = 183$, $A_{\perp} = 105.4$ and $A_{\text{av}} = 114.45$. The covalency parameter α^2 is calculated to be 0.91. The observed data show that g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are closer to 2, and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This suggests major distortion in the Cu^{II} complex from octahedral geometry. The α^2 value for this complex is commensurate with considerable covalent character in σ -bonding, involving metal ion and ligand.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. 2-Hydrazinobenzooxazole was prepared¹⁵ by refluxing the

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ethanolic solution of 2-mercaptobenzooxazole with hydrazine hydrate. The ligand was obtained as pale yellow coloured needle-like crystals by refluxing the hydrazino compound with benzil in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol, yield 80%, m.p. 171°.

$[M(BOAIDE)(H_2O)_3]Cl$: To an ethanolic solution of appropriate hydrated metal(II) chloride, ethanolic solution of ligand (HBOAIDE) was added in 1 : 1 proportion and the pH was adjusted at 8–8.5. All the complexes which precipitated out were digested on a steam bath. They were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused $CaCl_2$, m.p. >250°.

$[M(BOAIDE)L_3]Cl$: To an ethanolic suspension $[M(BOAIDE)(H_2O)_3]Cl$, pyridine or picolines (α, β, γ) was added dropwise under reflux till a clear solution was obtained. It was then allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature. The residue left after evaporation of the solvent was washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused $CaCl_2$, m.p. >250°.

Molar conductance was measured on a Toshniwal CL 01-06 conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (dioxane)¹⁶ on Shimadzu 180 and Carl-Zeiss-Jena spectrophotometers, ESR spectra on a Varian Associate 109 spectrometer (100 KHz, X-band (RT), scan range 2.0×1 and field set 3200), ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a JEOL GSX 400 spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature. Thermogravimetric analysis was done with a Netzsch-429 analyzer.

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